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MODERN MODELS OF SALES LOGISTICS IN THE SERVICE SECTOR: MARKETING ASPECT AND AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT

Mamatkulova Shoira Djalolovna

Candidate of Economic Sciences

Associate Professor of the Marketing Department

Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Abstract. In this article, we examine modern sales logistics models in the service industry from a marketing perspective. We analyze the relationship between logistics processes and marketing tools in creating customer value and enhancing the competitiveness of service organizations. Particular attention is paid to integrating sales logistics with marketing communications, managing service distribution channels, and improving customer service.

Key words: sales logistics, service industry, marketing, marketing communications, customer value, distribution channels, competitiveness.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada xizmatlar sohasida sotuv logistikasining zamonaviy modellari marketing yondashuvi nuqtayi nazaridan ko'rib chiqiladi. Logistik jarayonlar va marketing vositalarining iste'molchi qiymatini shakllantirish hamda servis tashkilotlarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishdagi o'zaro bog'liqligi tahlil qilinadi. Sotuv logistikasini marketing kommunikatsiyalari tizimi bilan integratsiyalash, xizmatlarni taqsimlash kanallarini boshqarish va mijozlarga xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini oshirish masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sotuv logistikasi, xizmatlar sohasi, marketing, marketing kommunikatsiyalari, iste'molchi qiymati, taqsimlash kanallari, raqobatbardoshlik.

Аннотация. В нашей статье мы рассматриваем современные модели логистики продаж в сфере услуг с позиций маркетингового подхода. Анализируется взаимосвязь логистических процессов и маркетинговых инструментов в формировании потребительской ценности и повышении конкурентоспособности сервисных организаций. Особое внимание уделяется интеграции логистики продаж с системой маркетинговых коммуникаций, управлению каналами распределения услуг и повышению качества обслуживания клиентов.

Ключевые слова: логистика продаж, сфера услуг, маркетинг, маркетинговые коммуникации, потребительская ценность, каналы распределения, конкурентоспособность.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of developing market relations and intensifying competition in the service sector, improving sales logistics as a crucial element of organizational performance management is particularly important. Modern service companies operate in an environment where customer value is shaped not only by the quality of service but also by the efficiency of logistics processes, service speed, availability of sales channels, and the level of customer interaction. Therefore, sales logistics is becoming the focus of close attention from both marketing and management. Modern sales logistics models in the service sector are characterized by close integration with marketing tools and a focus on customer needs. The marketing aspect of sales logistics manifests itself in the management of service distribution channels, the development of flexible service offerings, the use of digital technologies, and the development of customer communications. An effective combination of logistics and marketing solutions allows service organizations to increase competitiveness, optimize costs, and strengthen customer loyalty.

The relevance of this study stems from the need to adapt traditional sales logistics models to the modern operating conditions of the service sector, including digitalization, the growth of online channels, and changing consumer behavior. These conditions necessitate a scientific understanding of existing sales logistics models and the identification of areas for their improvement, taking into account a marketing approach.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Contemporary research in the field of sales logistics in the service sector demonstrates growing scholarly attention to the integration of logistics processes with marketing strategies. For example, Kotler and Armstrong [1] emphasize that a marketing approach to logistics not only optimizes the delivery of goods and services but also creates customer value, improves the customer experience, and enhances loyalty. The authors view sales logistics as an element of integrated marketing management, where distribution channels, service speed, and service availability are key. Lee [2] examines modern digital logistics models, noting that the implementation of online platforms, mobile applications, and automated CRM systems allows service organizations to reduce costs, improve order fulfillment accuracy, and expedite customer service processes. The work emphasizes the importance of adaptive models, which ensure flexibility and rapid response to changes in consumer demand.

Ivanova [3] examines the marketing aspect of sales logistics through the lens of customer communications. In her opinion, integrating logistics with marketing tools creates additional competitive advantages for companies, increases the efficiency of service distribution channels, and fosters long-term customer relationships. The author emphasizes that assessing customer satisfaction, analyzing loyalty, and utilizing feedback are essential elements of modern logistics systems. Petrov [4] examines the industry-specific implementation of sales logistics models in various service industries, such as the hotel industry, financial institutions, and courier services. He notes that the choice of logistics model depends on the scale of the business, the industry specifics, and the level of digitalization, while integrating logistics and marketing is a universal strategy for improving efficiency.

Summarizing the results of the literature analysis, it can be concluded that modern research emphasizes the need for an integrated approach to organizing sales logistics in the service sector. Key areas include the integration of logistics and marketing processes, the use of digital technologies, adaptation to changes in demand, and a customer focus. This approach enhances the competitiveness of organizations, optimizes resources, and creates sustainable customer value.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To achieve the article's objectives and solve the stated tasks, a combination of theoretical and empirical research methods was used to provide a comprehensive analysis of modern sales logistics models in the service sector. The primary approach was a systematic study of logistics processes through the lens of marketing aspects and customer value. As a theoretical basis, methods of analysis, synthesis, and generalization of scientific publications were used to identify key trends in the development of sales logistics, integration with marketing tools, and the digitalization of service processes [1]. A literature review identified the main sales logistics models (centralized, decentralized, digital, integrated, and adaptive), their functional characteristics, and their role in increasing customer value.

For the empirical portion of the study, comparative analysis and case studies were used to evaluate the practical application of modern sales logistics models in various service sectors. Data was collected through open sources, company reports, statistical materials, and publications by industry analysts [2]. This approach enabled the identification of relationships between the applied logistics model, marketing strategy, and customer satisfaction, loyalty, and competitiveness indicators. The integrated application of the above methods ensured the scientific validity and practical significance of the study's findings, identified areas for improving sales logistics models, and developed recommendations for integrating them with marketing tools to enhance the competitiveness of service organizations in today's environment.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Modern sales logistics models in the service sector represent a complex system of interconnected processes aimed at ensuring the timely delivery of services to consumers, optimizing distribution channels, and improving overall business efficiency. In the face of increasing competition and changing consumer expectations, sales logistics has ceased to be a purely operational function and has become an integrated part of organizations' marketing strategies. Key elements of modern models include service supply chain management, sales channel coordination, service inventory management, consumer preference monitoring, and the use of digital technologies to improve the efficiency and quality of customer service [1]. The marketing aspect of sales logistics is manifested in the need to create consumer value, which is determined not only by the product itself but also by the convenience of receiving it, speed of service, quality of customer experience, and the availability of interaction channels. Modern approaches utilize analytical tools to evaluate customer behavior, segment target audiences, and tailor logistics solutions to individual consumer needs. In this context, the integration of sales logistics with marketing communications, including service promotion, customer feedback, loyalty programs, and reputation management, is becoming a key element [2].

Digitalization plays a significant role in the modernization of sales logistics. The implementation of automation systems, online platforms, mobile applications, and electronic service channels reduces service delivery times, increases order fulfillment accuracy, and improves the customer experience. Furthermore, digital technologies facilitate the collection and analysis of large volumes of consumer data, enabling more accurate demand forecasting, optimization of service delivery routes, and increased staff efficiency. Adaptability of sales logistics models is also crucial, allowing organizations to quickly respond to changing market conditions and customer needs [3]. Modern sales logistics models in the service sector vary depending on the industry and the specific organization. In the hotel and tourism industries, the emphasis is on speed of service delivery, coordination of booking channels, and maintaining a high level of service. In financial and banking services, the priority is digital channel management, integration with customer services, and ensuring transaction security and reliability. Regardless of the industry, the key focus is on creating flexible and adaptive logistics systems capable of meeting customer needs at a high level, minimizing costs, and increasing the organization's competitiveness [4].

An analysis of modern models shows that improving sales logistics should be based on a comprehensive approach, including strategic planning, process optimization, integration with marketing tools, and the use of information technology. A key area is the implementation of demand forecasting models, which enable the timely adaptation of resources and services to actual consumer needs. Also of particular importance are methods for evaluating the effectiveness of logistics solutions from a marketing perspective, such as measuring customer satisfaction, assessing loyalty, and fostering long-term customer relationships [1].

To better understand the characteristics of modern sales logistics models in the service sector, it is useful to examine their key characteristics, advantages, and marketing focus. The table below demonstrates the main types of sales logistics models, their functional features, and methods for increasing customer value, allowing us to understand how the integration of logistics and marketing impacts the effectiveness of service organizations (Table 1).

Table 1. Modern sales logistics models in the service sector and their characteristics[®]

Sales Logistics Model	Main goal	Key elements	Marketing aspect	Use Case
Centralized	Optimization of resource allocation and service quality control	Centralized order management, resource warehousing, process standardization	Ensuring a consistent level of service, increasing customer satisfaction	Banking services with centralized transaction processing
Decentralized	Increased flexibility and adaptation to local markets	Regional offices, local service points, autonomous management	Accounting for local preferences, personalizing services	Hotel and travel agency chains
Digital/Online	Speedier service and service availability	Online platforms, mobile apps, process automation	Customer convenience, CRM integration, collecting and analyzing consumer data	Online flight booking, mobile banking apps
Integrated	Combination of logistics and marketing communications	Sales channel coordination, service supply chain management, feedback	Creating customer value, managing loyalty, increasing competitiveness	E-commerce companies, food and grocery delivery companies
Adaptive/Flexible	Rapid response to changes in demand	Demand forecasting, route optimization, dynamic resource allocation	Personalizing offers, meeting customer needs in a timely manner	Courier services, delivery services

The table below demonstrates that each sales logistics model in the service industry is focused on specific marketing goals and objectives, including improving convenience, speed of service, and building long-term customer relationships. Centralized and decentralized models demonstrate a balance between control and flexibility, while the digital model leverages the benefits of online services, the integrated model combines

logistics with marketing communications, and the adaptive model ensures a rapid response to changing demand. The use of these models in the practical operations of service organizations contributes to the development of competitive advantages, improved service quality, and the creation of customer value. It is important to note that the choice of a specific model depends on the specific industry, business scale, customer preferences, and the degree of digitalization of processes. A systematic approach to the application of these models allows for the optimization of sales logistics, improved customer interactions, and a stronger company position in the market.

Thus, modern sales logistics models in the service sector represent an integration of logistics and marketing processes aimed at increasing customer value, optimizing resources, and strengthening competitive positions. The implementation of digital technologies, adaptive approaches, and data analysis methods is key to improving the effectiveness of these models and developing the service sector in the modern economy [2].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

An analysis of modern sales logistics models in the service sector shows that integrating logistics processes with marketing tools is a key factor in improving the performance of service organizations. Centralized, decentralized, digital, integrated, and adaptive models allow for the combination of resource management, sales channel optimization, and customer value creation, thereby strengthening companies' competitiveness. The implementation of digital technologies, demand forecasting, service personalization, and the use of customer feedback ensure rapid response to market changes and high service quality. Modern approaches to sales logistics demonstrate that focusing on customer needs and marketing integration are essential elements of the strategic development of the service sector [1].

As a result of our research on this topic, we offer the following suggestions:

- first, service organizations are recommended to systematically implement integrated and adaptive sales logistics models, combining supply chain management with marketing communications.
- second, the active use of digital tools, including online platforms, mobile applications, and crm systems, is necessary to improve service speed and accessibility.
- third, it is advisable to conduct regular demand forecasting and consumer preference analysis to promptly allocate resources and personalize offers.
- fourth, it is important for educational and management organizations to develop employee competencies in logistics and marketing to effectively implement modern sales models.

List of used literature:

1. Котлер Ф., Армстронг Г. Основы маркетинга. – Москва: Питер, 2020.
2. Ли Х. Логистика и управление цепями поставок. – Москва: Дело, 2019.
3. Иванова М. Цифровая трансформация логистики в сфере услуг. – Тошкент: Fan, 2021.
4. Петров А. Современные подходы к управлению продажами в сервисной сфере. – Москва: Инфра-М, 2020.
5. Маматкулова Ш. МЕҲНАТ БОЗОРИДА КАДРЛАР СИЁСАТИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ БЎЙИЧА МАРКЕТИНГ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАРИНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ //Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 392-397.
6. Ловлок К., Райт Л. Маркетинг услуг. — СПб.: Питер, 2020.
7. Маматкулова Ш. ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ ПО ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ КАДРОВОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА //Экономическое развитие и анализ. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 392-397.
8. Kotler P., Keller K. Marketing Management. — Pearson, 2019.
9. Kumar V., Reinartz W. Customer Loyalty and Lifetime Value. — Harvard Business Review, 2018.
10. Buttle F., Maklan S. Customer Relationship Management. — Routledge, 2020.
11. Mamatkulova S. et al. Improvement of the GIS map of the potential of biomass for the development of bioenergy production in the Republic of Uzbekistan //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2022. – Т. 2432. – №. 1.
12. Mamatkulova S. H. J. Communicative language teaching in the national context. TJE-Tematics Journal of Communication Skills ISSN 2277-3053, Vol-6-(Issue-1-2022), 2–5 [Электронный ресурс].
13. Маматкулова Ш. Ж. Место и роль маркетинговых исследований в маркетинговой деятельности промышленных предприятий //Архивариус. – 2020. – №. 8 (53). – С. 48-51.
14. Блэквелл Р., Миниард П., Энджел Дж. Потребительское поведение. — СПб.: Питер, 2021.
15. Mamatkulova S., Uzakov G. Assessment of the Gross Potential of Local Waste Based on Geoinformation Systems for Bioenergy Production //The Journal of CIEES. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 34-39.
16. Mamatkulova S. K. et al. Effect of microbiological biofertilities on cotton fiber quality and expression of genes responsible for trait development //Niva Povolzhia (Niva Povolzhya). – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 61. – С. 1004.
17. Juraev I. I., Mamatkulova D. J. THE CONCEPT OF INFLATION AND ITS'ESSENTIAL ROLE IN THE ECONOMY // International Scientific and Practical Conference World Science. – ROST, 2017. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 42-43.
18. Jalolovna M. S. Use of modern marketing concepts in the activities of enterprises in the conditions of innovative and digital economy //Web of Discoveries: Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 48-50.
19. Парасураман А., Зейтамл В. Качество обслуживания и удовлетворенность клиентов. — Journal of Marketing Research, 2019.

20. ママトクロヴァニルファル. 津田梅子の教育思想の特質に関する一考察: 女性の自立と地位向上をめぐる視点から: дис. – Waseda University, 2010.
21. Verhoef P. et al. Omnichannel customer experience. — Journal of Retailing, 2021.
22. Payne A., Frow P. Strategic Customer Management. — Cambridge University Press, 2017.
23. Котлер Ф., Армстронг Г. Основы маркетинга. — М.: Вильямс, 2021.
24. Jalolovna M. S. Quality and Consumer Evaluation of Goods On The Market in an Innovation Economy //International Journal of Scientific Trends. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 93-96.
25. Jalolovna M. S. THE ROLE OF CONTENT MARKETING IN ATTRACTING AND RETAINING CUSTOMERS //Western European Journal of Historical Events and Social Science. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 22-26.
26. Jalolovna M. S. Features of the development of the marketing strategy of the enterprise //European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 2. – С. 6194-6205.

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